

Synthesis and characterization of titaniumnaphthoquinolates and their [4+2]-cycloadducts

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Manuscript received 26 December 2002, revised 17 July 2003, accepted 12 September 2003

The titanium chelates of naturally occurring hydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinones have been synthesized and their [4+2]-cycloadditions with 1,3-dienes have also been investigated.

Recently, the Diels-Alder cycloaddition reactions of quinones have been reported from our laboratory¹. Therefore, in continuation of our interest in chelate chemistry of 1,2- and 1,4-quinones², we have extended these reactions to titanium chelates of *ortho*- and *para*-hydroxyquinones followed by their Diels-Alder cycloaddition reactions.

Results and discussion

Synthesis of metal chelates :

The reaction of titanium alkoxide **1** with hydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinones **2a-c** [lawsone **2a**, juglone **2b** and plumbagin **2c**] in the molar ratio of 1 : 2 in anhydrous benzene afforded the complexes **3a-c** (Scheme 1); the liberated isopropanol being removed azeotropically and was estimated by oxidimetric method. These reactions are quantitative and quite facile. All these derivatives are brown/violet solids and have been further purified by recrystallization from a mixture of chloroform and *n*-hexane (1 : 3). The chelates are soluble in common organic solvents and are highly susceptible to hydrolysis.

Scheme 1

The chelates appeared to have five **3a** or six-membered **3b, 3c** cyclic structures. The five membered ring is formed

in case of lawsnates, whereas six membered chelation is present in juglonates and plumbaginates.

Synthesis of [4 + 2]-cycloadducts :

Since the quinonoid double bond in these chelates remains intact, the chelates **3b-c** were subjected to Diels-Alder cycloaddition with 1,3-dienes **4a-b** to produce corresponding cycloadducts **5a-d** (Scheme 2), which were characterized by spectral studies.

Scheme 2

UV-visible spectra :

The UV-visible spectra (EtOH) of the free ligands **2a-c** showed mainly three bands at 215–225, 250–265 and 430–450 nm assignable to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$, $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ (C-OH) and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ (quinonoid) transitions respectively. In the spectra of the corresponding chelates, $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ band remained unaffected, while the second band shifted to lower wavelength (225–230 nm) due to the formation of Ti-O bond. The third band underwent hypochromic shift due to the introduction of Ti moiety in the system which distorted the geometry. In the case of Diels-Alder cycloadducts **5a-d**, $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ (quinonoid) band shifted towards shorter wavelength (420–425 nm) (hypsochromic shift) which may be due to the removal of conjugation in the quinonoid ring.

IR spectra :

In the IR spectra of the chelate **3**, disappearance of absorption band around 3200 cm^{-1} due to phenolic group indicated chelate formation by the deprotonation of -OH group. Two types of carbonyl absorptions were observed : one in the higher region $\sim 1680\text{--}1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to free $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ group while the co-ordinated carbonyl group appeared in the lower region around $1630\text{--}1620\text{ cm}^{-1}$ as a strong band. Aromatic stretching band for the quinone ring appeared in the region of $1560\text{--}1580\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The additional band at 480 cm^{-1} for the Ti-O bond, further supported the chelate formation.

NMR spectra :

In the ^1H NMR spectrum (CDCl_3) of chelate **3b**, the absence of the signal for phenolic -OH protons in the region of $\delta 7.4\text{--}12.5$ ppm, further supported the formation of chelate through C-5 hydroxyl group. Two doublets at $\delta 6.4$ and 6.9 corresponded to two quinonoid protons, aromatic protons appeared as a multiplet in the region of $\delta 7.3\text{--}8.2$ ppm. Formation of cycloadduct **5a** was supplemented by the absence of signals for quinonoid protons in the range of $\delta 6.2\text{--}7.0$ ppm. The isopropoxy methyl protons ($4 \times \text{CH}_3$) appeared as doublet at $\delta 0.92$ ppm, methyl protons ($4 \times \text{CH}_3$) appeared as singlet at $\delta 1.5$ ppm, methylene protons ($4 \times \text{CH}_2$) appeared as multiplet at $\delta 2.15$ ppm, whereas methine protons ($4 \times \text{CH}$) appeared as a triplet at $\delta 2.21$ ppm. The isopropoxy methine protons appeared as a multiplet in the range of $\delta 3.18\text{--}3.48$ ppm. The aromatic protons ($6 \times \text{ArH}$) were seen as a multiplet in the range of $\delta 7.8\text{--}8.1$ ppm.

The ^{13}C NMR spectrum (CDCl_3) of chelate **3b**, displayed signals for quinonoid carbons in the range $\delta 178\text{--}168$, aromatic carbons appeared at $\delta 140\text{--}132$ whereas olefinic carbons resonated at $\delta 129\text{--}125$, isopropoxy carbon (OCHMe_2) and the methyl carbons were noticed at $\delta 78.2$

and $\delta 28.4$ ppm, respectively.

All these assignments are in harmony with the assigned structure.

Antimicrobial activity :

All the synthesized compounds have been screened for their antibacterial activities using *Streptomycin* as the reference drug. Disk diffusion method of Varma *et al.*³ has been followed. The bacteria used were *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. Results obtained has been summarized in Table 1. All the compounds showed moderate to high activities and it may be attributed to the presence of quinonoid-tin chelation.

Table 1. Antibacterial activity of the synthesized compounds (activity index)

Compd.	Zone of growth inhibition (mm)	
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
3a	9.5	8.0
	(1.05)	(1.04)
3b	7.5	9.0
	(1.02)	(1.83)
3c	7.5	9.5
	(1.06)	(1.5)
5a	9.0	8.0
	(0.94)	(1.07)
5b	8.5	9.5
	(0.98)	(0.97)
5c	9.0	10.0
	(1.02)	(1.77)
5d	8.0	7.5
	(1.06)	(0.98)

Reference drug for antibacterial activity – *Streptomycin*.

Activity index = Inhibition zone of test sample/inhibition zone of standard.

Experimental

Throughout the work, apparatus with standard interchangeable glass joints were used. Extreme care was taken to exclude moisture from the apparatus. Fractionations were carried out in a column, 30 inches long, packed with rasching rings and fitted to a total condensation variable takeoff stillhead. Alkoxides of organotitanium were prepared and purified by the standard methods.

Titanium isopropoxide (Aldrich) was distilled (b.p. 234°) before use. The solvents were dried using standard methods⁴.

Titanium was estimated gravimetrically⁵. Isopropoxy group was estimated by oxidation with acidified potassium dichromate⁶. IR spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Nicolet-Magna 550 spectrophotometer and ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spec-

tra on a Jeol FX 90 Q FT spectrometer (90 MHz).

Representative method for the synthesis of metal chelate (3b) :

To a benzene solution of the ligand **2b** (0.70 g, 4.0 mmol) was added metal isopropoxide (**1**; 0.57 g, 2.0 mmol) in anhydrous benzene (~50 ml). The resulting violet solution was refluxed on fractionating column for 6 h. Progress as well as completion of the reaction was monitored by the estimation of isopropanol collected azeotropically with benzene by oxidimetric titrations⁶. After stripping off the solvent under reduced pressure the product was isolated as dark violet solid m.p. 135° (0.91 g, 72%).

Representative method for the synthesis of cycloadduct (5b) :

To a solution of chelate **3b** (0.51 g, 1.0 mmol) in benzene (10 ml), isoprene **4a** (0.20 g, 2.94 mmol) in the same solvent (5 ml) was added dropwise and the resultant solution was set aside for 48 h in dark at RT. The colour of the reaction mixture changed to light violet and solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure to afford the violet cycloadduct **5b** (0.38 g, 62%).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. R. C. Mehrotra for valuable guidance and studentship to one of the authors (I.S.) under SAP Programme. Financial assistance from D.S.T., New Delhi to the other author (D.K.) is gratefully acknowledged.

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